

SPIRE: Structure-Preserving Interpretable Retrieval of Evidence

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Abstract

Retrieval-augmented generation over semi-structured sources such as HTML is constrained by a mismatch between document structure and the flat, sequence-based interfaces of today’s embedding and generative models. Retrieval pipelines often linearize documents into fixed-size chunks before indexing, which obscures section structure, lists, and tables, and makes it difficult to return small, citation-ready evidence without losing the surrounding context that makes it interpretable.

We present a structure-aware retrieval pipeline that operates over tree-structured documents. The core idea is to represent candidates as subdocuments: precise, addressable selections that preserve structural identity while deferring the choice of surrounding context. We define a small set of document primitives—paths and path sets, subdocument extraction by pruning, and two contextualization mechanisms. Global contextualization adds the non-local scaffolding needed to make a selection intelligible (e.g., titles, headers, list and table structure). Local contextualization expands a seed selection within its structural neighborhood to obtain a compact, context-rich view under a target budget. Building on these primitives, we describe an embedding-based candidate generator that indexes sentence-seeded subdocuments and a query-time, document-aware aggregation step that amortizes shared structural context. We then introduce a contextual filtering stage that re-scores retrieved candidates using locally contextualized views.

Across experiments on HTML question-answering benchmarks, we find that preserving structure while contextualizing selections yields higher-quality, more diverse citations under fixed budgets than strong passage-based baselines, while maintaining scalability.

1 Introduction

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) has become the dominant paradigm for grounding language-model outputs in external evidence. Yet most RAG pipelines begin by discarding the very structure that makes documents intelligible: HTML pages, technical manuals, and reference articles are flattened into sequences of fixed-size text chunks before indexing. This linearization erases section boundaries, heading hierarchies, list and table structure, hyperlinks, and other conventions that authors rely on to organize meaning. The result is a retrieval system that can find textually similar spans but cannot reason about where those spans sit within a document, what structural context they depend on, or how to present them as self-contained evidence.

The cost of this mismatch is most visible when retrieved evidence must be shown to a user as a citation. A sentence lifted from the middle of a numbered list, stripped of its list heading

and surrounding items, is often unintelligible. A table cell without its row and column headers is meaningless. A paragraph whose topic is established only by its section title becomes ambiguous. These are not edge cases; they are the norm for semi-structured web documents, where meaning is distributed across the structural hierarchy rather than concentrated in individual spans.

This paper introduces a retrieval framework that treats document structure as a first-class object throughout the pipeline. We parse HTML documents into tree-structured representations and assign every node a stable, path-based identifier. These paths serve simultaneously as citation-ready addresses and as the primitive that retrieval algorithms use to select, merge, and expand evidence. Rather than committing to a flat rendering at indexing time, we work with *subdocuments*—path-addressed selections whose contextualization is postponed until it is needed.

The framework is organized around two complementary forms of contextualization. *Global contextualization* enriches a retrieved node with the non-local structural scaffolding required to make it interpretable in isolation: the document title, enclosing section headers, list or table structure, and similar cues that are logically associated with the node but may be distant in the tree. This global context is computed deterministically from the document structure and prepended to each candidate at embedding time, producing embeddings that encode both content and structural position. *Local contextualization* operates after retrieval, expanding a sentence-level selection into its surrounding structural neighborhood. An LLM-based filtering step then examines this expanded view to retain only the material relevant to the query, yielding compact, context-rich excerpts. Crucially, path identifiers are maintained through both stages, so that the final citations point precisely to their source locations regardless of how much context was added or removed during retrieval.

Figure 1 illustrates the interaction between global and local context. The initial vector search returns sentence-level results that are rendered with their global context. Subsequent stages merge these results and selectively expand them to incorporate local context, yielding excerpts that are both structurally grounded and semantically complete. This separation between global and local context allows retrieval algorithms to reason explicitly about different sources of interpretability, rather than conflating them through fixed-size chunking.

This two-stage design—global context for indexing, local context for refinement—addresses a tension that runs through much of the RAG literature. Retrieving at a fine granularity (e.g., individual sentences) yields precise hits but strips away context; retrieving at a coarse granularity (e.g., large blocks) preserves context but dilutes relevance and wastes budget on unhelpful material. Our approach resolves this by decoupling the granularity of *matching*—which operates over globally contextualized sentences—from the granularity of *presentation*, which is determined by local expansion and filtering under a token budget.

We situate this work within several threads of prior research. Classical structured-document retrieval, notably the INEX initiative [8], established the problem of returning sub-document elements at appropriate granularity from XML collections, but predates neural embeddings and generative models. Recent hierarchical retrieval systems such as RAPTOR [21] build retrieval trees via clustering and summarization, but construct the tree from content rather than exploiting the document’s own authored structure. Similarly, Dense X Retrieval [5] shows that finer-grained retrieval units (propositions) outperform coarser passages. This result supports our choice of sentence-level retrieval, although their setting assumes flat documents rather than tree-structured ones. Other work also reports gains from finer-grained citation and retrieval units [26, 13]. Anthropic’s contextual retrieval [1] enriches chunks with LLM-generated context summaries before embedding—an approach whose spirit our global contextualization shares, but which we implement deterministically from document structure, making it cheaper, reproducible, and provenance-preserving. Late chunking [10] takes a complementary approach, encoding entire documents through a long-context transformer before chunking the token embeddings so that each chunk inherits document-wide context via

(1) First result sentence

Explore The Natural Beauty Of State Parks In Virginia [*@H1*]

Did you know **Virginia has over 41 state parks** bursting with **diverse landscapes** ? [*@H1, @S*]

(2) Second result sentence

Explore The Natural Beauty Of State Parks In Virginia [*@H1*]

Key Takeaways [*@H1, @H2*]

- Virginia has over 41 state parks with **diverse landscapes**, offering natural beauty and **outdoor activities** [*@H1, @H2, @B1*].

(3) Merging of first two result sentences

Explore The Natural Beauty Of State Parks In Virginia [*@H1*]

Did you know **Virginia has over 41 state parks** bursting with **diverse landscapes**? [*@H1, @S*]

Key Takeaways [*@H1, @H2*]

- Virginia has over 41 state parks with **diverse landscapes**, offering natural beauty and **outdoor activities** [*@H1, @H2, @B1*].

(4) Expansion of the merged result sentences

Explore The Natural Beauty Of State Parks In Virginia [*@H1*]

Did you know **Virginia has over 41 state parks** bursting with **diverse landscapes**? [*@H1, @S1*]

This blog will guide you through some of Virginia’s most scenic state parks, highlighting their **unique attributes and attractions**. [*@H1, @S2*]

Key Takeaways [*@H1, @H2*]

- Virginia has over 41 state parks with **diverse landscapes**, offering natural beauty and **outdoor activities**. [*@H1, @H2, @B1*]
- Some of the top state parks in Virginia include Grayson Highlands State Park, Shenandoah River State Park, Mason Neck State Park, Kiptopeke State Park, Pocahontas State Park, Natural Bridge State Park, and First Landing State Park. [*@H1, @H2, @B2*]
- Scenic attractions within Virginia’s state parks include Luray Caverns, Natural Tunnel State Park, Westmoreland State Park, Burke’s Garden, the New River Trail State Park, Breaks Interstate Park, the Great Dismal Swamp, Sand Cave in Cumberland Gap National Historical Park, and Great Falls Park. [*@H1, @H2, @B3*]
- Visitors can enjoy various **outdoor activities** at Virginia’s state parks, such as hiking trails, camping, fishing, wildlife viewing, picnicking, and swimming. [*@H1, @H2, @B4*]

Figure 1: Sample excerpts generated while retrieving for the query: “How many state parks are there in Virginia?”. Items (1) and (2) show the initial results returned by vector search, where each result corresponds to a single sentence. In both cases, the sentence is rendered together with its *global context*, which here consists of the document title and, for the second sentence, the enclosing section header (“Key Takeaways”). Item (3) illustrates the next stage of the pipeline, in which these two sentence-level excerpts are merged into a single combined excerpt. Finally, item (4) shows an expansion of the merged excerpt that supplies additional *local context*, incorporating content that is spatially adjacent (above and below) to the merged region in the original document. The labels shown in $\{ \dots \}$ are meta-level annotations included only for demonstration: each token denotes a structural element in the displayed context (e.g., *@H1* = document title, *@H2* = section header, *@B1* = first bullet item), and these labels are not internal symbols of the algorithm. They are used to visualize what the contextualization rules include; for example, [*@H1, @H2, @B1*] in item (3) indicates that global contextualization of bullet *@B1* pulls in its enclosing header *@H2* and title *@H1*.

attention. Sentence-window and parent-document retrieval patterns decouple retrieval granularity from synthesis granularity, but use flat offsets or fixed parent–child mappings; our contextual filtering follows the document tree and applies LLM-based filtering, with post-retrieval reranking following the retrieve-then-rerank paradigm established by neural passage reranking [17]. On the citation side, work on attributed generation [4, 9] and fine-grained citation [26, 6] focuses on teaching models to produce or verify citations, whereas our framework provides structurally grounded citation units by construction. Finally, work on context-window utilization [14, 12] shows that LLM performance degrades as context length grows and when relevant information is buried in the middle, motivating our approach of retrieving focused, structurally contextualized fragments rather than large document blocks.

We make the following contributions:

1. A **path-addressable document model** with a small set of primitives—paths, path sets, subdocument extraction, and two contextualization operators—that form a general interface between tree-structured documents and sequence-based models.
2. A **structure-aware retrieval pipeline** that indexes globally contextualized, sentence-seeded subdocuments; merges co-located results at query time; and applies local contextualization with LLM-based filtering to produce compact, citation-ready excerpts.
3. **Experimental evidence** on HTML question-answering benchmarks (HotpotQA and ASQA) showing that preserving structure yields higher-quality, more diverse citations under fixed token budgets compared to strong passage-based baselines, and that the contextual-filtering stage substantially improves citation precision.

2 Path-addressable document model

Our goal for this section is to lift retrieval to a level of abstraction at which retrieval systems can operate directly over tree-structured documents. This section focuses on the representation side of that story: we introduce a small collection of primitives that let us name and extract fine-grained evidence from an HTML-like tree while preserving enough structure to keep the extracted result well formed and interpretable. These primitives serve as a common interface between document structure and the sequence-based APIs of current models; the next section uses them to define the retrieval algorithms themselves.

We proceed in four steps. First, we define a path-addressable document model in which every node in a document tree carries a stable, prefix-ordered path. Paths are citation-ready identifiers, and finite path sets let us denote non-contiguous selections of nodes as a single unit of retrieval. Second, we formalize a subdocument extraction operator that turns an arbitrary path set into a well-formed subtree by completing the structural context required to interpret the selection. Third, we introduce global contextualization policies, with a concrete policy for HTML, that enrich path sets in a principled, idempotent way before extraction. Fourth, we introduce our approach to local contextualization, which expands a given path set to include nearby content in the document.

2.1 Document trees and paths

We represent each source as a *document* with explicit tree structure. Formally, a document is a value of the inductive datatype **Doc**:

$$\mathbf{Doc} ::= \mathbf{Text}(s) \mid \mathbf{Elem}(tag, attrs, [\mathbf{Doc}]).$$

Here $\mathbf{Text}(s)$ is a leaf carrying the string s , and $\mathbf{Elem}(tag, attrs, [\mathbf{Doc}])$ is an interior node that carries an HTML-like tag, an attribute map, and an ordered list of child documents. Because this representation subsumes HTML, it provides a practical, uniform encoding for a broad range of document types [7, 15].

To avoid ambiguity between a whole document and a particular node within it, we treat nodes as positions in a document, identified by document paths. A *document path* is a finite list of child indices; we write path concatenation as $p \cdot [i]$. Given a document D , we define $\mathbf{Paths}(D)$, the set of valid paths in D , and $D[p]$, the (sub)document rooted at path p , inductively:

- The root position has the empty path $[]$, and $[] \in \mathbf{Paths}(D)$ with $D[[]] = D$.
- If $p \in \mathbf{Paths}(D)$ and $D[p] = \mathbf{Elem}(tag, attrs, [D_1, \dots, D_k])$, then for each $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ we have $p \cdot [i] \in \mathbf{Paths}(D)$ and $D[p \cdot [i]] = D_i$.

Thus, when we refer to “a node in D ”, we mean a path $p \in \mathbf{Paths}(D)$, and $D[p]$ names the corresponding subtree. These paths are fine-grained, citation-ready identifiers for document content.

Example 2.1 (Document tree and paths). *The HTML document in Listing 1 parses to the document tree shown in Listing 2. Each subtree is annotated with its path; for example, the text of the first paragraph is identified by the path $[0, 0, 1, 0]$.*

Listing 1: Tiny HTML document.

```
<html>
  <body>
    <section>
      <h1>Title</h1>
      <p>First paragraph.</p>
      <p>Second paragraph.</p>
    </section>
  </body>
</html>
```

Listing 2: Document tree of the HTML document in Listing 1.

```
Elem("html", {}, [
  Elem("body", {}, [
    Elem("section", {}, [
      Elem("h1", {}, [
        Text("Title",
          path=[0,0,0,0])
      ]),
      Elem("p", {}, [
        Text("First_paragraph.",
          path=[0,0,1,0])
      ]),
      Elem("p", {}, [
        Text("Second_paragraph.",
          path=[0,0,2,0])
      ]),
    ])
  ])
])
```

Whereas a single path identifies one node, retrieval and citation typically involve multiple, non-contiguous regions of a document. We therefore work with finite collections of paths. A *path set* is a finite subset $P \subseteq \mathbf{Paths}(D)$. Path sets allow us to refer to groups of document nodes, such as several paragraphs, list items, or table cells, as a single unit of extraction, retrieval, or citation.

Path sets give us a compact way to name multiple, possibly non-contiguous, regions of a document. However, an arbitrary path set does not by itself guarantee that these regions can be interpreted meaningfully as part of a document tree. In practice, two kinds of structural completion arise repeatedly when working with path sets:

- A selected node must be reachable from the root of the document. If a path is included but one of its ancestors is missing, then the node cannot be reached by descending the tree.
- A selected structural node is often intended to stand for its entire contents, not just the node boundary itself. For example, selecting a paragraph typically means selecting its text as well.

We capture these two forms of completion using two simple path-set operations:

- *Ancestor completion.* Given a document tree D and a path set P , the operation $\text{Up}(D, P)$ adds all ancestor paths required to reach every path in P from the root. Intuitively, Up ensures connectivity.
- *Descendant completion.* The operation $\text{Down}(D, P)$ adds all descendant paths of each path in P that occur in D . Intuitively, Down ensures that selecting a structural node includes its internal contents.

These two operations address complementary structural concerns, and we will often apply them together. We write

$$\text{Link}(D, P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Up}(D, P) \cup \text{Down}(D, P)$$

for this ancestor–descendant closure.

Example 2.2 (Ancestor and descendant completion). *Let D be the document tree in Listing 2.*

Ancestor completion. Suppose $P = \{[0, 0, 1]\}$, selecting the first paragraph node. Then $\text{Up}(D, P)$ adds the paths needed to reach this node from the root:

$$\text{Up}(D, P) = \{[], [0], [0, 0], [0, 0, 1]\}.$$

Descendant completion. Applying descendant completion to the same set adds the paragraph’s text node:

$$\text{Down}(D, P) = \{[0, 0, 1], [0, 0, 1, 0]\}.$$

Closure. Taking their union yields

$$\text{Link}(D, P) = \{[], [0], [0, 0], [0, 0, 1], [0, 0, 1, 0]\},$$

which recovers both the structural context and the internal content associated with the selected node.

2.2 Subdocuments

Documents rarely need to be sent to a generative or an embedding model in their entirety. Instead, we want to extract a small, well-formed subdocument from a source document D given an intensional description of relevant content as a set of paths $P \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)$. A path set by itself is only a pointer-like representation (useful for naming and scoring); to feed evidence to a model, or to render it for a reader, we must materialize it as an actual document tree.

We do so in two steps. First, we enrich P with the structural context needed for interpretation (at minimum via ancestor–descendant closure $\text{Link}(D, P)$, and later via global-contextualization policies). Second, we extract the corresponding subdocument by deleting everything outside the enriched set. This second step is implemented by a pruning operator: it is not an alternative to path sets, but the mechanism that turns a chosen set of paths into a concrete subtree.

Definition 1 (Pruning operator). *Let D be a document tree and let $P \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)$ be a set of paths to keep.*

We define an auxiliary pruning operator that prunes the subtree rooted at a path r :

$$\text{PruneAux}(D, r, P) = \begin{cases} D' & \text{if } r \in P, \\ \varepsilon & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where

$$D' = \begin{cases} \mathbf{Text}(s) & \text{if } D[r] = \mathbf{Text}(s), \\ \mathbf{Elem}(tag, attrs, children) & \text{if } D[r] = \mathbf{Elem}(tag, attrs, [\cdot]), \end{cases}$$

and

$$children = [\text{PruneAux}(D, r \cdot [i], P)]_{r \cdot [i] \in P}.$$

The bracketed child list discards any ε results and preserves the original child order.

Finally, the (two-argument) pruning operator is defined by starting at the root:

$$\text{Prune}(D, P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{PruneAux}(D, [], P).$$

Intuitively, $\text{Prune}(D, P)$ keeps exactly the nodes whose paths lie in P , and removes everything else. In practice, P must include enough ancestry to reach the nodes of interest.

Example 2.3 (Prune: keep two non-contiguous blocks (both paragraphs)). *Let D be the tree in Listing 2. Consider the keep set*

$$P = \{[], [0], [0, 0], [0, 0, 1], [0, 0, 1, 0], [0, 0, 2], [0, 0, 2, 0]\}.$$

This keeps the two paragraph subtrees but drops the heading subtree at $[0, 0, 0]$. The result of $\text{Prune}(D, P)$ is shown in Listing 3.

Listing 3: Both paragraphs only of our document in Listing 2 (heading removed).

```
Elem("html", {}, [
  Elem("body", {}, [
    Elem("section", {}, [
      Elem("p", {}, [
        Text("First_paragraph.", path=[0,0,1,0])
      ]),
      Elem("p", {}, [
        Text("Second_paragraph.", path=[0,0,2,0])
      ])
    ])
  ])
])
```

The example above already hints at what is awkward about using `Prune` directly: to keep a node deep in the tree, the keep set must explicitly include all of its ancestors. If we omit an ancestor, pruning cannot even reach the desired node.

Example 2.4 (Prune: missing ancestry yields an unintended cut). *Let D be the tree in Listing 2 and take*

$$P = \{[], [0], [0, 0, 1], [0, 0, 1, 0]\},$$

which tries to keep the first paragraph but forgets the `section` node at path $[0, 0]$. Then $\text{Prune}(D, P)$ cannot descend from $[0]$ to $[0, 0, 1]$, so the result collapses to Listing 4.

Listing 4: Result of pruning with a keep set that omits required ancestors.

```

Elem("html", {}, [
  Elem("body", {}, [
    ])
  ])
]

```

Now, with `prune` and `link`, we define our subdocument operator. Intuitively, a subdocument is the smallest well-formed document tree that contains the selected nodes together with the structural context needed to interpret them. The definitions above make this intuition precise without requiring upstream algorithms to reason directly about tree invariants.

Definition 2 (Subdocument). *Given a document tree D and a set of target paths $P \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)$, the subdocument determined by P is*

$$\text{Subdoc}(D, P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Prune}(D, \text{Link}(D, P)).$$

We illustrate the construction using the tiny HTML document and tree from Listings 1–2.

Example 2.5 (Subdocument: isolate a single paragraph). *Let $P = \{[0, 0, 1]\}$, selecting the first paragraph node.*

Ancestor completion adds the paths needed to reach this node from the root, while descendant completion adds the paragraph’s text node. Thus,

$$\text{Link}(D, P) = \{[], [0], [0, 0], [0, 0, 1], [0, 0, 1, 0]\}.$$

Pruning with this linked set yields the subdocument consisting of exactly the first paragraph and its minimal context.

Example 2.6 (Subdocument: non-contiguous blocks). *Suppose we wish to keep both the document title and the second paragraph. Let $P = \{[0, 0, 0, 0], [0, 0, 2, 0]\}$.*

Linking adds the necessary ancestors for both targets, producing a path set that connects them through the document structure. Pruning then yields a subdocument that contains these two blocks together, even though they are not contiguous in the original document. The result is shown in Listing 5.

Listing 5: Subdocument: document title and second paragraph.

```

Elem("html", {}, [
  Elem("body", {}, [
    Elem("section", {}, [
      Elem("h1", {}, [
        Text("Title",
          ])
      ])
      Elem("p", {}, [
        Text("Second paragraph.",
          ])
      ])
    ])
  ])
]

```

In much of what follows, we will work not with a materialized subdocument $\text{Subdoc}(D, P)$, but instead with the pair (D, P) itself. At first glance, this may appear to be merely a trivial representation of a path set, and it is worth explaining why this choice is both intentional and important.

The key observation is that subdocument construction is typically not something we want to perform eagerly. Materializing $\text{Subdoc}(D, P)$ requires traversing and copying parts of the document tree, an operation whose cost is proportional to the size of the resulting tree. In contrast,

most upstream algorithms, such as global and local contextualization, operate by transforming or comparing path sets, not by inspecting the concrete tree structure itself.

For this reason, we refer to the pair (D, P) as a *subdocument*: it denotes the intention to extract the subdocument induced by P , without actually performing the extraction yet. All intermediate operations manipulate only the path set P , while the underlying document D remains fixed. The subdocument operator is applied only at the final stage, when we are ready to render or serialize the result, for example, when constructing the input to an embedding or a generative model.

Formally, the only invariant required of a subdocument is that its path set be valid with respect to the document:

$$P \subseteq \text{Paths}(D).$$

This invariant is preserved by all of the transformations we consider. As a result, subdocuments provide a uniform and lightweight interface for reasoning about partial documents, while postponing the cost of tree materialization until it is strictly necessary.

In the remainder of the paper, we therefore write (D, P) when referring to a subdocument under construction, and reserve $\text{Subdoc}(D, P)$ for the final, materialized tree that is passed to downstream consumers.

2.3 Global contextualization

Even when structurally sound, a subdocument may omit nearby contextual cues, such as titles, section headers, list scaffolding, etc., that are important or even essential for interpretability of its contents. The presence or absence of such cues substantially affects the quality of retrieval and downstream reasoning.

To ensure that contextual information is reinstated when needed, we treat context enrichment purely at the level of path sets. Starting from any subdocument (D, P) , a *global contextualization* augments P with additional paths mandated by a concrete policy θ . Applying this enriched path set to the earlier subdocument operator yields a well-formed, context-aware tree.

Definition 3 (Global contextualization). *Let (D, P) be a subdocument. A global contextualization for policy θ is a function*

$$\text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, \cdot) : 2^{\text{Paths}(D)} \rightarrow 2^{\text{Paths}(D)}$$

satisfying, for all subdocuments (D, P) :

Extensivity $P \subseteq \text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P)$.

Monotonicity *If $P \subseteq P'$, then $\text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P) \subseteq \text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P')$.*

Idempotence $\text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, \text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P)) = \text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P)$.

Because $\text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P)$ is defined to be a subset of $\text{Paths}(D)$, it follows that global contextualization always preserves subdocuments. Given a policy θ , the context-enriched subdocument derived from (D, P) is

$$\text{Subdoc}(D, \text{GlobalCtx}_\theta(D, P)).$$

In the remainder of this section, we present the global-contextualization rule for HTML titles in full detail, and then give summaries of the corresponding rules for headers, lists, and tables. The complete HTML global-contextualization policy is obtained by composing these individual rules. This composition is well behaved: because each rule is extensive, monotone, and idempotent, their composition preserves these properties and therefore defines a valid global-contextualization operator.

2.3.1 Titles

Our first instance of global contextualization brings in the document title, wherever it might be located in the document tree, either in a `title` section or, if there is none, in a header section.

Definition 4 (Title global contextualization). *Let D be a document tree. The title global contextualization $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{title}}(D)$ is a fixed set of paths that provides document-wide context when no targets are selected. We adopt the HTML-oriented policy:*

$$\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{title}}(D) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} \{\text{TitlePath}(D)\}, & \text{if a document title exists,} \\ \{\text{H1}(D)\}, & \text{if a top-level heading exists but no document title exists,} \\ \{\}, & \text{otherwise (empty context).} \end{cases}$$

Here $\text{TitlePath}(D)$ is the unique path to the document `<title>` node (if any), and $\text{H1}(D)$ is the path to the first `<h1>` node in document order (if any).

Example 2.7 (Title global context on the tiny tree). *On the tiny document from Listings 1–2, we typically have $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{title}}(D) = \{[0, 0, 0]\}$ (the `<h1>` at path $[0, 0, 0]$). Thus:*

$$\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{title}}(D) = \{[0, 0, 0]\}.$$

2.3.2 Headers

Beyond the document title, headers provide the most important form of global context in structured documents. Unlike titles, which apply to the whole document, headers scope their influence to the material that follows them. When a subdocument selects a node, only the headers that are in effect at that point in the document should be included in its context.

A complication is that, in HTML, header scoping is not determined purely by tree ancestry. Headers such as `<h1>`–`<h6>` introduce regions of influence that extend forward in document order and are terminated by later headers of the same or higher rank. As a result, a paragraph may be governed by a header that is not its ancestor in the DOM tree, but instead precedes it linearly. Correctly recovering this structure requires reasoning about document order and header levels rather than tree structure alone.

Our header global-contextualization rule captures this behavior by identifying, for each selected path, the set of headers that are *active* immediately before that path in document order. Intuitively, these are the headers one would encounter by scanning backward from the selected node, keeping the most recent header at each level while discarding any that are superseded by intervening headers of equal or higher rank. The global contextualization then adds exactly these active headers to the path set.

This rule yields context that matches standard HTML reading semantics: content under a section inherits its enclosing headers even when those headers are not ancestors in the tree.

2.3.3 Lists

Lists introduce a subtle form of context because their semantic structure does not align cleanly with simple subtree containment. In HTML, nested lists are encoded by placing a sublist (`` or ``) inside a list item (``). As a result, a list item may simultaneously serve as a label for a group (e.g. “Lunch”) and as the structural parent of a nested sublist (e.g. “Sandwich”, “Salad”).

```
<ol> <li>Lunch <ul> <li>Sandwich</li> <li>Salad</li> </ul> </li> </ol>.
```

Naively applying ancestor or descendant closure in this setting either drops essential labels or pulls in unrelated sibling items.

The key challenge is to include enough list structure to preserve meaning without introducing extraneous siblings. When a subdocument selects an item deep in a nested list, we typically want to retain (i) the item itself and its immediate content, and (ii) the textual labels of enclosing list items that give the item its hierarchical position. At the same time, we want to avoid including other items from the same nested list unless they are explicitly selected.

Our list global-contextualization rule addresses this by treating list items asymmetrically. For the innermost enclosing list item, the rule keeps the minimal path from that item down to the selected node, preserving the item’s own content. For each enclosing list item further out, the rule keeps only the leading children that precede any nested sublist. This retains the label text (e.g. “Lunch”) while excluding the nested list itself, thereby preventing sibling items such as “Sandwich” from being pulled into the subdocument.

This construction yields context that matches standard reading semantics for nested lists: selected items are accompanied by the labels that situate them, but not by unrelated siblings.

2.3.4 Tables

Tables are tricky for global contextualization because a single cell is rarely meaningful in isolation: its interpretation depends on the row and column labels that name what the cell is “about.” At the same time, pulling in an entire HTML table can be extremely expensive in tokens, and much of the table (empty cells, unrelated rows, decorative structure) is irrelevant when we are rendering or scoring cells independently.

Our policy therefore treats table context as a lightweight labeling problem rather than a reconstruction problem. When a seed path set selects a table cell (`<td>` or `<th>`), we augment the path set with just the corresponding row label and column label cells, when they can be identified. Concretely, we locate the enclosing table and row for the selected cell and determine its column position within that row; we then add the leftmost header cell in the row (row label) and the topmost header cell in the column (column label). This yields a minimal context that makes the selected cell intelligible when rendered.

The key consequence is that the contextualization does not pull in other data cells or the full table skeleton. It adds only directly referenced labels, keeping the result compact while preserving the associations that matter for downstream use (e.g., embedding or generative-model scoring of individual cells).

2.3.5 HTML-aware global contextualization

Thus far we have specified global-contextualization rules targeted at particular HTML structures, that is, titles, headers, lists, and tables. These rules capture the minimal dependencies needed for a fragment to be intelligible. However, our downstream uses of global contextualization typically require a single, uniform notion of global contextualization that we can apply to any seed set of paths. As a first, deliberately simple step, we define a composite rule that merely takes the union of the four specialized policies.

We refer to this rule as the *HTML-aware global contextualization* and write it $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{HTML}}(N, P)$.

Definition 5 (HTML-aware global contextualization). *Let (D, P) be a subdocument. Write*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{HTML}}(N, P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} & P \cup \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{title}}(N) \\ & \cup \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{hdr}}(N, P) \cup \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{lst}}(N, P) \cup \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{tbl}}(N, P). \end{aligned}$$

The operator simply aggregates whatever additional paths each specialized rule would introduce: (i) title-level context via $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{title}}(N)$ (as specified in the title subsection), (ii) enclosing-section scaffolding via $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{hdr}}(N, P)$, (iii) list spines via $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{lst}}(N, P)$, and (iv) table labels via $\text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{tbl}}(N, P)$. Because each constituent is extensive, monotone, and idempotent on its domain, their union is again a global-contextualization operator.

2.3.6 Potential for extensibility

We illustrated a policy for global contextualization drawn from familiar HTML structure. The larger point is that the mechanism is extensible: a contextualization policy can be specialized to other document idioms without changing the subdocument pipeline. One common and feasible specialization is worth highlighting. Many technical and legal documents maintain a dedicated section where terms are defined (e.g., a glossary or “Definitions”). In HTML this is routinely encoded with stable cues: anchors/IDs on definition blocks, `<dfn>` or `<dt>/<dd>` pairs, or lightweight data-attributes. A glossary-aware policy can: (i) pre-index definitions by canonical term (and synonyms, if annotated); (ii) recognize term mentions in the body via explicit links, `<dfn>` references, or scoped annotations; and (iii) add the corresponding definition block (and optionally a small, fixed neighborhood as scaffolding) to the context whenever a mention appears in P . Because this policy only adds well-identified paths, it preserves the basic algebraic properties of global contextualization (extensive, monotone, idempotent with memoization) and integrates cleanly with masked pruning to include definition shells without dragging in unrelated content.

2.4 Local contextualization

Global contextualization enriches a selected path set with non-local structural scaffolding (e.g., titles, active headers, list spines, and table labels) so that an extracted view remains interpretable. However, even an interpretable subdocument can be too small to serve as a self-contained unit of evidence for downstream components. For example, a sentence-level selection is often precise but underspecified without nearby sentences or the surrounding paragraph.

We therefore introduce a complementary mechanism that expands a subdocument using only local structural neighborhoods in the document tree, with the goal of producing a compact but context-rich view under a target budget (e.g., a token budget for a chosen model). We refer to this process as *local contextualization*. Given a subdocument (D, S) , the goal is to derive a transient expanded view (D, P) that:

1. includes S ;
2. approaches a target input size (e.g., in terms of words, tokens, etc.);
3. respects document structure, favoring complete sentences, paragraphs, and block-level elements; and
4. preserves path stability, so that results from different expansions can be compared and combined.

Local contextualization and global contextualization are orthogonal and can be composed: the former grows a selection outward in place, while the latter adds structural cues that may be essential for interpretation.

Local contextualization proceeds by gradually enlarging the path set S using structural relations in the document tree. At each step, we consider adding surrounding context drawn from:

- sentence completion, to avoid dangling fragments;
- enclosing block-level elements (e.g., paragraphs, list items); and
- nearby regions in document order.

Each candidate expansion is evaluated by rendering the resulting subdocument and estimating its size under the chosen size function (e.g., a tokenizer). Expansion continues until the rendered view is close to the target size, or no further admissible growth is possible without exceeding it.

Contrast with fixed-size chunking. Many retrieval pipelines rely on fixed-size chunkers that partition documents into overlapping spans of tokens or characters prior to indexing. Such chunkers are agnostic to document structure: they may split paragraphs, interleave unrelated sections, or duplicate content across overlapping windows. In contrast, our expansion mechanism operates after an initial selection, starts from a precise subdocument, and grows outward in a structure-aware fashion, prioritizing complete sentences, paragraphs, and block-level elements. This lets us tailor the presented context to a target budget without committing to a single, global chunking of the corpus.

3 Structure-aware retrieval pipeline

This section connects the document model developed in the previous section with retrieval techniques familiar from the literature on RAG. Our aim is twofold. First, for readers experienced with RAG, vector search, or hybrid retrieval pipelines, we show how our notion of subdocuments fits naturally into conventional embedding- and generative-model-based retrieval workflows. Second, for readers with a programming-languages background, we explain how ideas such as explicit structure, delayed materialization, and contextualization operators provide a principled foundation for retrieval over semi-structured documents such as HTML.

At a high level, our retrieval pipeline has two stages. An *embedding-based* stage performs high-recall similarity search over a fixed inventory of candidates. An optional *contextual filtering* stage then reasons over the retrieved candidates to refine or validate relevance. Although these stages can be used independently, we present them together to emphasize the role of subdocuments as a unifying representation.

Subdocuments as retrieval units. In our system, the natural unit of retrieval is the subdocument. This contrasts with many RAG pipelines, where the retrieval unit is typically a text span of some kind (e.g., byte/character offsets, line, column ranges, or other start/end indices into a flattened text view), or a pre-flattened hierarchy such as sections containing paragraphs containing sentences represented as strings. By using subdocuments, we preserve a precise connection to the original document structure, including semantically meaningful markup such as links and formatting, and we can represent retrieval units at many granularities (a sentence, a paragraph, a table cell, etc.) within a single uniform datatype.

We apply global contextualization and rendering only when required by downstream consumers, rather than treating the contextualized excerpt as the retrieval unit. Doing so would prematurely discard potentially useful structure: once a seed selection (say, a sentence or HTML element) is replaced by its global contextualization, we lose the ability to distinguish what was originally selected from what was added for intelligibility. Subdocuments therefore let retrieval operate over precise, structured selections while postponing contextual augmentation to the point where it is actually needed.

```

<section>
  <h2>Background</h2>
  <p>
    <sentence-beg/>
    Ada Lovelace wrote
    the first algorithm.
    <sentence-end/>
    <sentence-beg/>
    <a href="...">Her notes</a>
    described the Analytical Engine.
    <sentence-end/>
  </p>
</section>

```

Sentence seed:

$$S_b = \text{SentPaths}(D, b)$$

Subdocument:

$$(D, S_b)$$

Global contextualization:

$$P_b = \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{HTML}}(D, S_b)$$

Rendered for embedding:

$$\text{Render}(D, P_b)$$

Figure 2: Sentence-anchored subdocuments. Sentence boundaries are inferred and recorded using zero-width markers without altering the HTML tree. Each sentence induces a seed path set S_b , yielding a subdocument (D, S_b) that is stored in the embedding index (not contextualized). Global contextualization and rendering are applied only at embedding time, producing a self-contained excerpt suitable for similarity search while preserving a precise reference back into the original document structure.

3.1 Vector-embedding-based retrieval

We begin with vector-embedding-based retrieval, which provides an efficient and query-agnostic mechanism for candidate generation. As in standard RAG pipelines, we embed a fixed collection of units, embed the user query, and retrieve the most similar units. A key design choice is the unit of indexing. We use sentences as the embedding seeds: empirically, sentence-level units strike a good balance between precision and recall, while paragraphs are often too large and semantically mixed, which can dilute similarity signals and degrade retrieval quality. Broader context is added later by contextualization and expansion, rather than being baked into the indexed unit.

Indexing surface. Let $\mathcal{D} = \{D_1, \dots, D_m\}$ be a corpus of document trees. An *indexing surface* is a finite set

$$\mathcal{I} \subseteq \{(D, P) \mid D \in \mathcal{D}, P \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)\},$$

whose elements are subdocuments. In this section we assume that, for each document tree D , we can enumerate its sentences as path sets. Concretely, each sentence is identified by a begin path $b \in \text{Paths}(D)$ and a corresponding sentence seed path set $S_b \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)$ that selects exactly that sentence. Our embedding index stores the sentence-seeded subdocuments (D, S_b) .

From subdocuments to embeddings. Figure 2 illustrates our pipeline. Given a subdocument (D, P) (in our case, $P = S_b$), we:

1. apply HTML-aware global contextualization to obtain an enriched path set P' ;
2. materialize the subdocument (D, P') ;
3. render the result to a textual format of choice (our implementation uses Markdown); and
4. embed the rendered text.

Thus, the indexed unit and the embedded text are intentionally distinct: the former preserves precision and referential stability, while the latter provides enough context for semantic similarity.

3.1.1 Supporting sentence-level references

Unlike many RAG settings, our input documents do not come with sentence structure built in. HTML provides elements such as paragraphs, list items, and table cells, but these are often too coarse: a single paragraph may contain multiple unrelated sentences, while splitting paragraphs naïvely risks destroying inline structure such as hyperlinks or emphasized text. Our solution is to derive sentence structure while preserving the original HTML tree. As a preprocessing step, we apply an off-the-shelf sentence segmenter to the rendered text of each block-level leaf. The resulting character spans are then mapped back to the HTML tree, where we insert zero-width sentinel elements

`<sentence-beg/>` and `<sentence-end/>`

at the corresponding boundaries. These sentinels do not re-parent or duplicate content; instead, they annotate the existing structure with explicit sentence boundaries while preserving all semantic markup, including links and inline formatting. Each sentence is thereby associated with a distinguished begin-sentinel path b , and the set of paths belonging to that sentence can be recovered as

$$\text{SentPaths}(N, b) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \in \text{Paths}(N) \mid p \text{ is annotated with } b\}.$$

3.1.2 Query-time retrieval

At query time, the user query is embedded and compared against the vectors in the index, yielding an ordered list of subdocuments ranked by similarity. In our experiments (and in common RAG evaluations), results are presented under a fixed output budget (e.g., a token budget used to match passage-based baselines and to reflect downstream input limits). A naive strategy is therefore to take the top- k subdocuments (or to admit items greedily until the budget is exhausted) after applying global contextualization to each item independently.

In our setting, this naive strategy performs poorly because of an interaction between (1) precise, overlapping indexed units and (2) document-level global contextualization. Sentence-seeded subdocuments are intentionally fine-grained, so many highly ranked items can originate from the same document and share substantial structural scaffolding (document title, enclosing headers, list structure, etc.). If we global-contextualize and render each retrieved item in isolation, this shared scaffolding is repeatedly included and repeatedly charged against the budget. As a result, near-duplicate outputs from a single document can crowd out other relevant evidence and reduce effective recall across documents.

A typical failure mode looks like the following: the ranker returns two items from the same document early in the list, both of which global-contextualize to include the same title and first header. The earlier item contributes little beyond this shared context, while the later item contains the answer-bearing sentence under that header. Costing them separately can cause the shared title/header material to consume enough of the budget that the answer-bearing item is excluded, even though it was retrieved.

Example 3.1 (Redundancy under global contextualization). *Consider a document D with title Foo and a first section header $First\ header\ of\ Foo$. Suppose the similarity ranker returns two sentence-seeded subdocuments from D , $x_1 = (D, S_{b_1})$ and $x_2 = (D, S_{b_2})$, with x_1 ranked above x_2 . After global contextualization and rendering, both items include the same structural scaffolding:*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Render}(\text{Subdoc}(D, \text{GlobalCtx}_{\text{HTML}}(D, S_{b_i}))) &\approx \# Foo + \#\# First\ header\ of\ Foo \\ &+ (local\ content\ near\ b_i). \end{aligned}$$

If x_1 contains only a generic sentence under the header, while x_2 contains the answer-bearing sentence, then charging each rendered item independently can consume the budget on two near-duplicates whose shared title/header dominates their cost. In that case, x_2 may be excluded even though it was retrieved and ranked highly. Aggregating by document avoids this outcome: we union the path sets $S_{b_1} \cup S_{b_2}$, global-contextualize once for D , and render a single view that pays for the title and header once while retaining both sentences.

Document-aware aggregation. To avoid repeatedly paying for shared structure, we aggregate retrieved items at the document level before enforcing the final budget. Concretely, we:

1. retrieve an initial prefix of the similarity-ranked subdocuments;
2. group candidates by their source document tree D ;
3. for each document, merge candidate path sets by union to form one aggregated subdocument (D, P_D) ;
4. apply global contextualization once per document to each merged selection and compute its rendered cost; and
5. select the highest-ranked aggregated results whose combined cost fits the target budget.

If the selected, deduplicated set falls well below the target budget, we increase the retrieval-prefix bound and repeat, admitting additional candidates until the aggregated result set approaches the budget.

3.1.3 Summary

The output of query-time retrieval is a sequence of subdocuments, with at most one aggregated result per source document, whose combined post-contextualization cost respects the target budget while preserving the similarity ranking as closely as possible. This document-aware aggregation is crucial for retrieval over subdocuments: it amortizes shared structural context (titles, headers, scaffolding) that would otherwise be duplicated across many fine-grained hits from the same document, and it keeps embedding retrieval competitive with conventional passage-based baselines without sacrificing referential precision.

Our choice of sentences as the unit of embedding is not essential to our overall approach of using path-addressable subdocuments. Other units are compatible with our approach, including ones using mixed granularities, e.g., mixing sentence- and paragraph-level embeddings. The only requirement is that the unit be representable by a path set.

3.2 Contextual filtering

The embedding stage performs high-recall candidate generation over the full corpus \mathcal{D} , but it does so using small indexing units (in our case, sentence-seeded subdocuments). This granularity is useful for retrieval—it yields precise, citation-ready anchors—but it is often too small to support reliable downstream decisions. In particular, the relevance of a sentence frequently depends on nearby content (adjacent sentences, the enclosing paragraph, or a local list/table region), and this information is intentionally not part of the indexed unit.

For this reason, we introduce a second, query-time filtering stage that evaluates retrieved candidates in their local structural neighborhood. This stage does not search the corpus anew; it

operates on a finite set of candidates produced by embedding retrieval, which we call a subdocument surface:

$$\mathcal{S} \subseteq \{(D, P) \mid D \in \mathcal{D}, P \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)\}.$$

Each element of \mathcal{S} is a subdocument that precisely identifies a region of interest (often anchored at a sentence), but does not yet commit to a particular amount of surrounding context.

Why filtering needs local context. Embedding similarity can conflate fine-grained distinctions (dimension leakage), and sentence-level units are prone to ambiguity when viewed in isolation (references, scope, negation, and exceptions often sit just outside the sentence boundary). As a result, a candidate that appears highly similar at the sentence level may become clearly irrelevant once nearby context is included, and conversely, a candidate may only become interpretable when expanded to include its immediate neighborhood.

Filtering via local contextualization. The filtering stage therefore evaluates each candidate after expanding it with local context. Concretely, for each $(D, P) \in \mathcal{S}$ we derive an expanded view by applying local contextualization (structure-aware expansion) to obtain a larger path set P^+ that still contains P but includes nearby structural context. We then pass to a query-conditioned scoring function the expanded view, and have the function decide which candidates to retain and which to discard.

3.2.1 Scoring citations via generative language models

In our implementation this scoring function is implemented by a generative model, prompted with the query and the expanded view. After structure-aware expansion, the generative model is applied to each expanded view derived from a subdocument in \mathcal{S} . In each invocation, we present the model with the user query Q together with a single expanded view (D, P) , rendered to text. The task of the model is not to produce an answer directly, but to identify which parts of the view are essential for answering Q .

To make this task precise and robust, we expose the internal citation structure of the view explicitly. Before rendering, we identify a set of *citable units* within P , such as sentences, list items, or paragraphs, each corresponding to a path-stable region of the document. When rendering the expanded view, we wrap each such unit i with a lightweight, deterministic marker `<lab_i> ... </lab_i>` inserted on the fly, without modifying the underlying document tree.

The generative model is then instructed to return exactly the set of labels whose corresponding units are required to answer Q . Each label ℓ deterministically maps back to a path set $P(\ell) \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)$, yielding a citation $(D, P(\ell))$. Aggregating over all expanded views, we obtain the final citation set

$$C^* \triangleq \bigcup_{\text{expanded views}} \{(D, P(\ell)) \mid \ell \text{ selected by the model}\}.$$

Example: generative-model prompt from a subdocument. We illustrate how the running example from Figure 2 is presented to a generative model. Suppose the embedding-based stage retrieves the sentence-anchored subdocument (D, S_b) corresponding to the sentence “*Her notes described the Analytical Engine.*” Structure-aware expansion then produces a context-rich view (D, P) , including the enclosing paragraph and section header.

Before rendering, we identify sentence- or paragraph-level citable units within P and assign each a deterministic label. The resulting prompt presented to the generative model has the following form:

User query:
Who described the Analytical Engine?

Document excerpt:
Background

<lab_1>Ada Lovelace wrote the first algorithm.</lab_1><lab_2>Her notes described the Analytical Engine.</lab_2>

Instruction:
Select the labels of all excerpts that are required to answer the query.
Return only a JSON list of labels.

In this example, the generative model is expected to return ["lab_2"]. The label lab_2 deterministically maps back to a context-closed path set $P(\text{lab}_2) \subseteq \text{Paths}(D)$, yielding a citation $(D, P(\text{lab}_2))$. Crucially, although the model reasons over an expanded, rendered view, the citation is recorded in terms of the original subdocument structure.

This label-based protocol ensures that citation extraction is stable under re-rendering and robust to paraphrasing or normalization performed by the generative model. In contrast to schemes that ask the model to reproduce citation text verbatim and recover citations by string matching, our approach preserves a precise link to the original document structure. The generative model reasons over expanded, context-rich views, while citations are recorded as subdocuments with well-defined structural identity.

4 Experimental evidence

This section evaluates the retrieval algorithms proposed in the paper. Our experiments are organized around two questions. First, we ask whether our vector-embedding-based retrieval algorithm is competitive with a strong HTML-specific baseline, BGE, when both systems use the same embedding model and are evaluated under a fixed citation budget. Second, we evaluate whether augmenting embedding-based retrieval with a contextualized-filtering stage improves citation quality. Across both sets of experiments, we measure retrieval quality using an LLM-as-judge protocol that assesses whether individual citations are helpful for answering the query. Together, these experiments isolate the effects of citation granularity, global contextualization, and contextual filtering, and demonstrate how each contributes to producing higher-quality, budget-efficient citation sets.

4.1 Experimental setup

Rubric. We evaluate citation quality using an LLM-as-judge procedure. For each query–citation pair, we prompt a judge model to determine whether the citation is *helpful* for answering the query (binary decision). This evaluation style follows prior work; in particular, SelfCite [6] uses an LLM judge to assess citation quality. As in their setting, we validated the judge by manually inspecting a random sample of judgments for consistency and obvious failure modes. For all experiments reported here, the judge is *Qwen 3 235B Instruct* [18], and the prompt we use appears in Appendix A. We report results as #helpful/#total and the corresponding ratio.

Datasets. We evaluate on two QA benchmarks used in HtmlRAG: HOTPOTQA [25] and ASQA [22]. Following HtmlRAG [23], we use their released evaluation suites: for each benchmark, HtmlRAG samples 400 instances uniformly at random and augments each instance with HTML pages sourced via Bing search. We use this data as-is for all reported runs, so our results are directly comparable to the HtmlRAG baselines.

Model	HOTPOTQA	ASQA
<i>Embedding-only retrieval (1000-token citation budget)</i>		
BGE	336/1514 (0.222)	998/1658 (0.602)
EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL	479/2225 (0.215)	1236/2010 (0.615)
EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL_NOCTX	836/6077 (0.138)	767/1872 (0.410)
<i>End-to-end pipeline (embedding + contextual filtering)</i>		
SPIRE	538/822 (0.655)	1673/2058 (0.813)

Table 1: Evaluation results across embedding-only retrieval and the end-to-end pipeline. Each cell reports #helpful/#total citations (ratio), evaluated under a fixed 1000-token citation budget.

4.2 Vector-embeddings-based retrieval

Baseline system. We used the same implementation that was used as a baseline for the HtmlRAG [23]. BGE consists of the *BGE-Large-EN* embedding model together with the HTML-side algorithms released by the HtmlRAG authors. These algorithms are responsible for turning raw HTML pages into embed-able units that respect the embedding model’s input-length constraint (roughly a 500-token limit): (i) *lossless HTML cleaning* that removes clearly irrelevant content (e.g., scripts/styles) and compresses redundant structure; (ii) *block-tree construction* that groups the DOM into block-level units at a fixed granularity; (iii) *embedding-based block scoring* that embeds each block and ranks blocks by similarity to the query; and (iv) a *budgeted selection* procedure (often described as trim/fill) that retains the highest-scoring blocks while preserving enough surrounding HTML structure (e.g., required ancestor tags) to keep the pruned result well-formed. In our experiments, we ported this BGE pipeline verbatim from the HtmlRAG codebase, so the baseline reflects their intended implementation.

Our system. Our embedding-based retriever is EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL, an implementation of the approach we presented in Section 3.1. To isolate algorithmic differences rather than model differences, EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL uses the same embedding model as BGE. Most importantly for interpreting our comparisons, our system EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL uses the same *BGE-Large-EN* embedding model as BGE; thus, differences in performance isolate the effect of the retrieval algorithms around the embedding computation (e.g., how HTML is decomposed, context is preserved, and candidates are assembled), rather than differences in the embedding model itself. Given that the reported performance of BGE in HtmlRAG is within approximately 5% of the full HtmlRAG system across many settings (sometimes slightly better, sometimes slightly worse), suggesting that BGE is a meaningful proxy baseline for retrieval quality in that work. For sentence segmentation in EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL, we use the sentence tokenizer provided by the NLTK toolkit [3].

Results. Table 1 reports results for embedding-only retrieval under a fixed budget of 1000 tokens of rendered citation text. Each entry reports two quantities: #total, the total number of citations emitted by the system within this budget, and #helpful, the subset of those citations judged helpful by the LLM judge. Because different systems emit citations at different granularities, the value of #total may vary substantially across systems even though they operate over the same document collection and under the same token budget. Accordingly, the ratio #helpful/#total should be interpreted as the primary measure of citation quality, while absolute counts reflect how effectively each system utilizes the available budget.

Comparing BGE and EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL, we observe that their helpful-citation ratios are similar across datasets (e.g., 0.222 vs. 0.215 on HOTPOTQA and 0.602 vs. 0.615 on ASQA). However, EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL produces substantially more citations within the same 1000-token budget (e.g., 2225 vs. 1514 on HOTPOTQA). This difference arises from citation granularity: EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL embeds and reports citations at the level of sentences, while BGE operates at a coarser block level. Because block-level citations are typically longer, fewer of them fit within the fixed budget. Taken together, the results indicate that sentence-level retrieval enables EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL to deliver more helpful citations under the same budget, while maintaining comparable per-citation quality.

To better understand the impact of global contextualization, we collected results from an ablation of our system EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL_NOCTX, in which we disable global contextualization. The ablation results further clarify the role of our design choices. Disabling global contextualization in EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL_NOCTX yields noticeably lower helpful-citation ratios, indicating reduced precision. On HOTPOTQA, EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL_NOCTX nevertheless produces a larger absolute number of helpful citations; this effect is explained by the removal of global-contextualization material from the budget, which frees space for additional lower-ranked citations that still contain useful information.

To better understand the impact of using sentences for the unit of embedding, we collected results from an altered version of our system where instead we take the unit of embedding to be the *block leaf* element. Block leaves are the smallest block-level containers (e.g., a `<p>`, ``, or `<td>`) that still preserve all nested inline markup (links, emphasis, etc.) but do not contain other block-level regions. This makes them a natural place to run sentence segmentation without breaking HTML structure. Because block leaves may be arbitrarily long, they can exceed the input-length limit of the BGE embedding model. We therefore use the *Qwen 3 0.6B embedding model* [20] for our altered retrieval algorithm, which supports substantially longer inputs (up to 32k tokens), and was sufficient for all benchmark instances we tested. Our block-leaf-as-retrieval-unit version performs worse in terms of its ratio, which is 0.176. On HOTPOTQA, its total citation count is 1910, similar to the 1514 produced by BGE, reflecting their shared block-level granularity.

Overall, these results show that sentence-level retrieval combined with global contextualization provides the best balance between precision and coverage under a fixed citation budget, and that both coarser block granularity and the removal of global contextualization degrade citation quality in distinct ways.

4.3 End-to-end pipeline, with contextual filtering

We also study our full retrieval pipeline presented in Section 3.2. Our contextual filtering step, labeled SPIRE, uses an instruction-tuned language model to explicitly select evidentiary citations from a structured excerpt produced by embedding-based retrieval. In our experiments, we use the *Qwen 3 32B* model [24, 19]. The prompt used to drive our contextual filtering is shown in Appendix A. This prompt enforces a citation-first protocol: the model is instructed to select only those chunks whose content itself supports the query, to return a minimal set of such chunks, and to refrain from citing material based on prior knowledge or latent recall.

Operationally, SPIRE builds directly on EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL. For each query, we first run the embedding-based retriever and take the prefix of its ranked results whose combined rendered size fits within a 1000-token budget. This prefix is passed verbatim to the generative model as a structured excerpt, with chunk boundaries and identifiers preserved. Thus, SPIRE and EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL operate over exactly the same candidate material; the sole difference is the presence of an explicit generative evidence-selection stage.

Results. Table 1 reports results for the end-to-end pipeline, SPIRE, alongside the embedding-only systems under the same 1000-token citation budget. Across both datasets, SPIRE substantially improves helpful-citation ratios. On HOTPOTQA, SPIRE achieves a ratio of 0.655, compared to 0.215 for EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL under the same budget, and on ASQA the corresponding ratios are 0.813 and 0.615. These gains indicate that the contextual filtering is effective at discarding weak or irrelevant candidates and concentrating the available budget on direct evidence.

We also observe that SPIRE changes the effective granularity of what is counted as a citation. On HOTPOTQA, SPIRE reports fewer citations overall (822 vs. 2225 for EMBEDDING_RETRIEVAL), consistent with the prompt’s instruction to return minimal supporting sets. On ASQA, the total citation counts are of similar magnitude (2058 vs. 2010), suggesting that our contextual filtering is uncovering additional citations, which is thanks to the spatial expansion of local contextualization.

Overall, these results show that augmenting embedding-based retrieval with an explicit contextual-filtering stage yields markedly higher-precision citation sets while operating on embedding-derived candidates under an identical citation budget.

5 Related work

Structure-aware RAG. HtmlRAG [23] and our work share the goal of improving retrieval over HTML documents by leveraging document structure rather than treating HTML as flat text. However, the two approaches differ substantially in how structure is represented and exploited. HtmlRAG operates directly over raw HTML source, using a fixed pipeline of preprocessing, block construction, and pruning heuristics to produce embed-able fragments that fit within model input limits. In contrast, we treat HTML as an internal, tree-structured representation and define retrieval in terms of programmable subdocuments and global-contextualization policies that explicitly capture the structural assumptions under which document fragments are interpretable. This allows us to decouple embedding and generative models from HTML-specific heuristics, reason formally about context inclusion, and support multiple retrieval strategies over the same structural abstraction.

Our global contextualization concept takes inspiration from a blog post by Lin [13], which argues that naive vector-based retrieval over web documents often fails because many documents are written under conventions that assume surrounding context. In particular, the post observes that in sources such as manual pages, technical documentation, and reference guides, individual sentences or paragraphs are frequently not self-contained: their meaning depends on nearby headers, section scopes, lists, or other structural cues. As a result, retrieving an isolated span via embeddings alone can yield excerpts that are syntactically valid but semantically opaque. Our notion of global contextualization can be viewed as a generalization of this observation. We formalize global contextualization as a document-structural operation that systematically augments retrieved nodes with the minimal surrounding context required for interpretability, while remaining compositional.

In this work, we focused on global-contextualization rules for common HTML structures (e.g., section headers and list spines). A natural next step is to extend the framework with more domain-specific patterns while preserving the same abstraction boundary. This raises two concrete questions for future work: how much of the structure seen in real-world documents can be captured with such rules, and to what extent can LLMs help infer new rules automatically?

Subdocument. The term subdocument has appeared previously in the context of XML processing. Benedikt and Fundulaki [2] use the term to describe the result of *subtree queries*, where an XML document is filtered to produce a smaller document whose root-to-leaf paths are preserved from the original tree. Their notion of subdocument is driven by query composition and evaluation in

XML databases, whereas our use of subdocuments is operational: we treat them as programmable, path-addressed views over document trees that support incremental construction, cost-bounded context selection, and interaction with LLM and embedding pipelines.

Prior work in hypertext systems has long emphasized fine-grained identity for document fragments. The Dexter Hypertext Reference Model [11] provides a canonical abstraction for hypertext systems, distinguishing content, anchors, and links while deliberately abstracting away from the internal structure of documents. Dexter anchors may be understood as naming regions within a document, but the model does not prescribe how such regions should be rendered, contextualized, or materialized when detached from their source. In contrast, our work assumes an explicit tree-structured document model and focuses on the operational problem that Dexter leaves open: given an intensional description of a fragment, how to construct a concrete, well-formed document that preserves the structural assumptions under which that fragment is interpretable.

A similar emphasis on fine-grained fragment identity appears in Ted Nelson’s vision for hypertext and transclusion, most fully articulated in *Literary Machines* [16]. Nelson’s work motivates reuse by reference, provenance preservation, and portion-level addressing, but treats the semantics of fragment inclusion largely at a conceptual level. In particular, transclusion describes what it means to reuse a fragment, but not how to compute the minimal surrounding structure required for that fragment to stand alone when consumed outside its original context. Our notion of subdocuments addresses this gap by decoupling fragment identity (path sets) from fragment materialization (pruning after contextualization), yielding a precise extraction semantics that supports incremental construction, cost-bounded expansion, and reliable use in retrieval-augmented generation pipelines.

Citation generation. LongCite [26] and SelfCite [6] both study the problem of citation generation: prompting an LLM with long contexts and training/alignment so that it produces answers with fine-grained, sentence-level citations. Our contribution is orthogonal: we focus on retrieval over tree-structured HTML and on constructing citations as precise, well-formed, path-addressed document regions. The approaches are therefore complementary: LongCite/SelfCite improve how generators cite, while our framework improves what is retrieved and how citation regions are represented.

6 Conclusion

We presented a retrieval framework that treats document structure as a first-class concern throughout the retrieval pipeline. Rather than reducing HTML documents to flat sequences of text spans, our approach preserves their tree structure and introduces a small set of abstractions—path sets, subdocuments, and contextualization policies—that allow retrieval algorithms to reason simultaneously about semantic content and structural cues. This design enables the extraction of well-formed excerpts of a desired size that remain interpretable in isolation, while remaining compatible with both vector embedding models and generative language models.

Our experimental results demonstrate that these structural choices matter in practice. When evaluated under a fixed citation budget and using the same embedding model as a strong HtmlRAG-derived baseline, our embedding-based retriever achieves comparable per-citation quality while surfacing substantially more useful citations. This effect arises primarily from finer-grained citation units (sentences rather than blocks) combined with explicit global contextualization, which allows the system to utilize available budget more effectively. Ablation studies further confirm that both global contextualization and citation granularity play critical roles: disabling global contextualization reduces precision, while reverting to block-level retrieval forfeits the advantages of sentence-level selection.

We also showed that preserving structure enables an effective end-to-end retrieval pipeline that combines embedding-based search with contextual filtering. Under the same embedding-derived input and citation budget, the generative retrieval stage substantially improves helpful-citation ratios on both benchmarks, indicating that contextual filtering is able to aggressively filter weak candidates while retaining high-quality evidence. Importantly, this improvement is achieved without sacrificing provenance: citations remain tied to precise subdocuments, even though the contextual filtering reasons over expanded, context-rich views. This separation between reasoning context and citation identity is central to maintaining robustness and reproducibility in our full retrieval pipeline.

More broadly, our work suggests that retaining document structure is valuable not merely for improving chunking heuristics, but for expanding the space of retrieval operations themselves. By preserving elements such as sections, tables, lists, and hyperlinks as addressable structure, retrieval systems can express queries that are difficult or impossible once documents are flattened, including structure-sensitive constraints that directly support provenance-aware evidence selection. We believe these ideas point toward a more principled integration of structured documents into retrieval-augmented generation pipelines, and offer a foundation for future work at the intersection of information retrieval, document understanding, and programming language techniques for structured data.

A practical caveat is that our path-addressed document model is intended as a high-level specification, not an optimized storage format. In deeply nested documents, explicit root-to-node paths require space proportional to depth, and some path operations inherit that cost. In principle, implementations can reduce this overhead with compact node identifiers and shared-prefix encodings, while preserving the same retrieval semantics.

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A Prompts used in experiments

The following is the prompt we use for scoring citations via our LLM judge.

You are an expert evaluator who determines whether citations contain useful information for answering specific questions.

Your task is straightforward:

1. Read the QUESTION carefully - understand exactly what is being asked
2. Read the CITATION - analyze what information it contains
3. Answer: Does this citation help answer the question? (YES or NO)
4. If YES: Extract the specific part of the citation that helps
5. If YES: Identify which part of the question this citation addresses

EVALUATION PRINCIPLES:

****When to answer YES (helps_answer_question = true):****

- Citation contains facts, names, dates, or details that directly answer the question
- Citation provides information needed to verify or find the answer
- Citation discusses the specific entities, events, or concepts asked about
- Someone reading this citation would get closer to answering the question

****When to answer NO (helps_answer_question = false):****

- Citation only provides generic background without specific answers
- Citation discusses related but different topics

- Citation lacks the specific information the question asks for
- Citation is off-topic or tangentially related

****For helpful_citation_part (if YES):****

- Extract the EXACT text/quote from the citation that helps
- Be specific - quote the relevant sentences or phrases
- Include context if needed but focus on the helpful parts
- If multiple parts help, include all of them

****For answered_question_part (if YES):****

- Extract the EXACT words/phrase from the question text itself that gets answered
- DO NOT write a new sentence - copy the actual text from the question
- Example: If question is "What is the speed of light in a vacuum?", answer: "the speed of light in a vacuum"
- Example: If question is "Who won the Nobel Prize in Physics in 2023?", answer: "Who won the Nobel Prize in Physics in 2023" or just the specific part answered
- If citation answers the full question, return the full question text
- If citation answers only part, return just that portion of the question

****Reasoning:****

- Always provide clear reasoning for your decision
- Explain why the citation does or does not help
- Be specific about what information is present or missing
- Focus on relevance to the actual question asked

****Key Guidelines:****

- Be STRICT: Generic information != helpful answer
- Be PRECISE: Extract exact quotes, not paraphrases
- Be HONEST: If citation doesn't help, say NO
- Be SPECIFIC: Identify exactly what helps and what gets answered

The prompt listed below is the one we use during local contextualization for the purpose of citation generation.

You are an evidence selector. Your job is to choose which chunks in the EXCERPT contain evidence that answers the QUERY. You will see chunks labeled with tags like <chunk3> ... </chunk3>.

Return ONLY a valid JSON array of these OPENING TAGS as strings, copied exactly:

["<chunk3>", "<chunk1>"]

CRITICAL EVIDENCE RULE (anti-hallucination):

- ONLY cite chunks whose *content itself* supports the answer.
- Do NOT cite a chunk just because it triggers knowledge you already have.
- If the excerpt does not contain the needed evidence, return [].

What makes a GOOD citation set:

- A set of chunks which, when read together, contains enough information to answer the query fully OR partially.
- A reader should be able to recover the supported part of the answer using ONLY the selected chunks.

What makes a POOR citation set:

- Irrelevant chunks (topic mismatch, background with no claim support).
- Chunks that only contain a title/name/keyword without stating the relevant fact.
- Chunks that merely *hint* at the answer but do not contain the claim, evidence, or reasoning.
- Chunks selected because "the model knows the answer anyway."

Minimality rule:

- Select the MINIMAL set of chunks that provide evidence.
- Prefer chunks that contain the relevant claim explicitly (names, dates, definitions, numbers, etc.).

If evidence is incomplete:

- Return chunks that provide partial evidence (and omit irrelevant chunks).
- Do NOT fill gaps using prior knowledge; partial evidence is still evidence.

OUTPUT FORMAT RULES:

- Output EXACTLY ONE JSON array of strings.

- Strings must be opening tags exactly as they appear, e.g. "<chunk3>".
- No markdown fences. No extra keys. No commentary before or after the JSON.

Examples (illustrative; do NOT copy content, copy the behavior):

Example A: Complete evidence present

Excerpt contains:

```
<chunk2>"The DeLorean was created by John DeLorean."</chunk2>
```

Query: "Who created the DeLorean automobile?"

Correct output: ["<chunk2>"]

Example B: Partial evidence present

Excerpt contains:

```
<chunk1>"The DeLorean automobile was produced by the DeLorean Motor Company."</chunk1>
```

Query: "Who created the DeLorean automobile?"

Correct output: ["<chunk1>"]

(Explanation: This supports only a partial answer about the company; it does NOT name the creator.)

Example C: No evidence in excerpt

Excerpt contains:

```
<chunk3># John DeLorean</chunk3>
```

Query: "Who created the DeLorean automobile?"

Correct output: []

(Reason: a title/name alone does not state the relevant fact; citing it would rely on model knowledge.)

Example D: Model knows the answer but excerpt doesn't contain it

Query: "What is the capital of France?"

Excerpt contains:

```
<chunk0>"France is a country in Europe."</chunk0>
```

Correct output: []

(Reason: the excerpt does not contain "Paris"; do not cite based on prior knowledge.)

EXCERPT:

```
{excerpt_md}
```

QUERY:

```
{query}
```